

Anoplolepis custodiens Common Pugnacious Ant

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Insect

Size: 2 to 10 mm

Distribution:

The Common Pugnacious Ant is distributed across Africa in the following countries: Angola, Botswana, Democratic Republic of Congo, Kenya, Mozambique, Namibia, Somalia, South Africa, Tanzania, Zimbabwe.

Importance:

Anoplolepis custodiens plays a major role in seed dispersal in the fynbos regions of South Africa.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 16.14 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 0.88 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Flye

Genome Length: 0.22 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 90.6% [Single: 87.5%, Duplicated: 3.1%]

BUSCO database: eukaryota

Assembly N50: 26.35 kilobases

Contig number: 16 253

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